

Exploring the Relationships among Shopping Motivation, Shopping Behavior, and Post-Purchasing Behavior of Mainland Tourists toward Taipei Night Markets

Ren-Hua Kung, Jen-Chieh Liu, Chih-Teng Chang, Pei-Ti Chen

Abstract—The consumption capability of people in China has been a big issue to tourism business. Due to the increasing of China tourists, Taiwan's government rescinded the category of people in China and opened up the non-stopped airline from China to Taiwan. The "one-day traveling style between China and Taiwan" has formed, hoping to bring business to Taiwan. Night market, which shows foreigners the very local character of Taiwan, contains various merchandise for consumers to purchase. With the increasing numbers of non-stopped airline, visiting Taiwan's night markets has also been one of major activities to China's tourists. The purpose of the present study is to understand the consumer behavior of China tourists in tourist night markets in Taipei and analyze that if their shopping motives cause the different shopping behaviors and post-purchase satisfaction and revisiting intention. The results revealed that for the China tourists, the motives of significant influence to the shopping behaviors. Also, the shopping behaviors significant influence to the whole satisfaction and the whole satisfaction significant influence to post-purchase behavior.

Keyword—Shopping Motivation, Shopping Behavior, Satisfaction, Post-Purchase Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

SINCE the enactment of the first type Mainland tourists to Taiwan on July 4, 2008 (e.g. citizens from Mainland China can directly come to Taiwan), the number of Mainland tourists to Taiwan has been gradually increasing. This is reflected through the constantly full cross-strait weekday air schedules and the implementation of the direct shipping ferry on December 15, 2008 to promote Mainland tourists to Taiwan. According to the statistics by Taiwan National Immigration Agency, with the implementation of cross-strait weekday charter flights including types 1, 2, and 3, the total number of Mainland tourists to Taiwan in 2010 reached up to 1,188,929 people, which is dramatically higher than that of 601,754 in 2009. It is noted that the visits of Mainland tourists to Taiwan bring about economic prosperity to this country.

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Night markets have been long considered not only a vital part of Taiwan's nightlife but also the local culture which reserve essentially traditional features. The Taiwanese modern night markets not only retain traditional consuming culture but also integrate foreign country cultural characteristics including cuisine, clothes, etc. The "2010 Annual survey report on visitors expenditure and trends in Taiwan" by the Tourism Bureau Ministry of Transportation and Communications (M.O.T.C.) shows the highest consumption of Japanese tourists while indicating the strongest shopping power of Mainland tourists, mainly in staples or specialty products (33%), jewelry and jade (25%), and clothing accessories (10%). The top three favored sightseeing spots are night markets, Taipei 101 shopping area, and National Palace Museum. Hence, it is worth noticing that although shopping is seldom used as the main purpose of tourism activities, it is viewed as the general activities that tourists spend most time on [1]. Based on the aforementioned research motivation, this study mainly focuses on (1) understanding shopping motivation, shopping behavior, and post-purchasing behavior of Mainland tourists toward Taipei Night Markets and (2) exploring the relationships among shopping motivation, shopping behavior, and post-purchasing behavior of Mainland tourists toward Taipei Night Markets.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Shopping motivation

Motivation refers to the individual's intrinsic drive which is spurred into actions. The advent of this driving force is caused by the stress state resulted from unmet needs. Therefore, people are motivated to conduct behaviors in order to satisfy conscious or subconscious demands, reduce the tension, and release the internal pressures [2]. Concerning shopping motivations, [3] through an investigation on foreign tourists' motivation toward visiting Hong Kong for sightseeing and shopping indicate that shopping motivations include (1) attractive price, (2) product diversity, (3) products' good quality, (4) fashionable, unique /special/ attractive merchandise, (5) shopping habits, and (6) the purchase of products that their own countries do not have.

B. Shopping behavior

1) The relationship between motivation and behavior

The shopping motivation cannot be directly observed; instead, it is indirectly speculated and acknowledged through individual behaviors.

Therefore, motivation and behavior can be viewed as two sides that complement each other [4]. In addition, the concepts of motivation and behavior are closely related since behavior acts as external activities and motivation refers to the internal process of promoting individual activities.

2) The relationship between tourism and shopping behavior

The souvenirs themselves contribute a great part to help tourists memorize the experience during the trip; hence, tourists would feel relatively disappointed if they do not buy anything. In accordance with tourist preferences, the range of souvenirs bought is very extensive, being divided into five categories of pictorial image souvenirs, piece-of-the-rock souvenirs, symbolic shorthand souvenirs, marker souvenirs, and local product souvenirs [5].

C. Satisfaction

Satisfaction refers to the comparison of consumers' before-buying expectations on product performance and actual perceived feelings after using the products. When the results are consistency, customer will obtain satisfaction. On the contrary, dissatisfaction is produced [6]. It is noted that believes satisfaction to be an overall phenomenon and utilizes overall satisfaction as a single measurement [7]. However, satisfaction is argued to be a complex concept and diversified phenomenon, thus is divided into two measurements which are overall satisfaction and sub-item satisfaction [8]. This study adopts overall satisfaction as a single item to measure and evaluate consumers' overall satisfaction on using products. Hence, the item satisfaction is referred to as the satisfaction of each product attribute.

D. Post-purchasing behavior

According to the consumer purchase evaluation model proposed by [9], post-purchasing behavior is affected by the gap between consumers' expectations on product performance and their actual perceived satisfaction after using products. In other words, the cross-interaction between products' expected and actual performance will cause consumers to produce satisfied or unsatisfied post-purchasing behaviors. Satisfied consumers are observed to exert frequently better post-purchasing attitudes, higher purchase intention, and brand loyalty. Meanwhile, unsatisfied consumers tend to express behaviors like low post-purchasing attitude, low or no purchase intention, brand switching and complaints, and negative public praise.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Framework

Fig. 1 Research Framework

B. Research Hypothesis

- H₁:** Shopping motivation of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on shopping behavior.
- H₂:** Shopping behavior of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on overall satisfaction toward night market.
- H₃:** Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on satisfied post-purchasing behavior.
- H_{3,1}:** Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on satisfied post-purchasing behavior.
- H_{3,2}:** Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior.

C. Sampling

The Shihlin night market and Raohe street night market in Taipei are targeted to be the research sample of this study. Based on consulting with hotels for the itinerary of the Mainland tourist groups, the survey questionnaires are conveniently distributed in the breakfast time of the day before night market visits with effective assistance of the restaurant supervisors. Five dimensions being examined include (1) shopping motivation, (2) shopping behavior, (3) overall satisfaction, (4) post-purchasing behavior, and (5) population statistics. Reliability is assessed using pre-test. Concerning internal consistency, the results show high Cronbach α coefficient of shopping motivation (0.775) and shopping behavior (0.786), which is above the benchmark of 0.70 suggested by [10]. Therefore, a high internal consistency is confirmed.

IV. RESULT

The survey questionnaires were sent from October to December 2011 to 440 randomly selected Mainland tourists under hotels' consultancy and assistance. As a result, 276 usable responses out of 300 were received from participants who visited Shihlin night market and 110 usable responses out of 140 were received from participants who visiting Raohe street night market. In sum, a total of 386 valid questionnaires were received, indicating a valid response rate of 88%.

A. Sample Collection

Respondent's background information including gender, age, occupation, level of education, and monthly income was collected. Respondents' ages range from 41 to 50 years old. A majority of the participants were males, married, graduates from higher education, and were working in industrial fields and commerce with monthly income from 3001 to 4000 CNY dollars.

B. Shopping Motivation Analysis

The analysis results show the highest shopping motivation of Mainland tourists is "memories of Taiwan travel" (4.12), followed by "personal use" (4.00). The lowest shopping motivation obtained is "demonstration of personal wealth and status" (2.93).

C. Shopping Behavior Analysis

According to the analysis results, the achieved highest shopping behavior of Mainland tourists is on “purchasing snacks” (4.01), followed by “purchasing clothing” (3.70) and “purchasing distinctive products” (2.98).

D. Overall Satisfaction Analysis

The analysis results express the mean of overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists of 3.92 and standard deviation of 0.84, which demonstrates the satisfaction of Mainland tourists toward night markets' overall performance.

E. Post-purchasing behavior Analysis

In order to examine Mainland tourists' post-purchasing behavior toward night market shopping, this study categorized this dimension into satisfied and unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior. Consequently, a total of 355 satisfied tourists and 31 unsatisfied ones were classified.

1) Satisfied post-purchasing behavior analysis

The highest satisfied post-purchasing behavior of Mainland tourist is reflected through the survey item “I will recommend and disseminate Taipei night markets to friends” (4.14), followed by “I will choose Taipei night market if I have a chance to vote main sightseeing points of Taiwan” (4.11). The lowest post-purchasing behavior obtained belongs to the item “I will disseminate Taipei night market toward mass media” (3.70).

2) Unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior analysis

The survey item “I would suggest relatives not visit Taipei night markets” ranks highest in unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior of Mainland tourist (3.06), followed by “If I have a bad feeling or problems, I will directly react to shop assistant” and “I will complain to related units about the bad experience and ask for resolution or amends”.

In sum, the above analyses have proven that if the Mainland tourists have unsatisfied overall feelings toward night markets, they would not present unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior.

F. Hypothesis testing

1) Hypothesis H₁: Shopping motivation of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on shopping behavior

In this part, the purchase of snacks, female accessories, electronic products, clothing, handicrafts, and CD are regarded as dependent variables whilst nine items of shopping motivation are treated as independent variables to conduct multiple regression analysis.

The results achieved are as follows:

a) Purchasing snacks

According to the multiple stepwise regression analysis of purchasing snacks, the shopping motivation has a significant explanatory power on purchasing snacks ($F=265.855$, $P=0.000$). The adjusted explained variance is 67.4% ($R^2=0.676$, Adjusted $R^2=0.674$). The results show the valid explained variance of three factors of shopping motivation (“memories of Taiwan travel”, “personal use”, and “purchase

of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues”) on purchasing snacks.

b) Purchasing female accessories

According to the multiple regression analysis, the shopping motivation has a significant explanatory power on purchasing female accessories ($F=181.477$, $P=0.000$). The adjusted explained variance is 48.4% ($R^2=0.487$, Adjusted $R^2=0.484$). The results show the valid explained variance of two factors of shopping motivation (i.e. “bargaining enjoyment” and “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues”) on purchasing female accessories.

c) Purchasing electronic products

According to the multiple regression analysis, the shopping motivation has a significant explanatory power on purchasing electronic products ($F=172.326$, $P=0.000$). The adjusted explained variance is 57.2% ($R^2=0.575$, Adjusted $R^2=0.572$). The results show the valid explained variance of three factors of shopping motivation (i.e. “bargaining enjoyment”, “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues”, and “purchase of worthy collectible products”) on purchasing electronic products.

d) Purchasing clothing

According to the multiple regression analysis, the shopping motivation has a significant explanatory power on purchasing clothing ($F=25.385$, $P=0.000$). The adjusted explained variance is 16.0% ($R^2=0.166$, Adjusted $R^2=0.160$). The results show the valid explained variance of three factors of shopping motivation (“purchase of worthy collectible products”, “demonstration of personal wealth and status”, and “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues”) on purchasing clothing.

e) Purchasing handicrafts

According to the multiple regression analysis, the shopping motivation has a significant explanatory power on purchasing handicrafts ($F=32.649$; $P=0.000$). The adjusted explained variance is 24.7% ($R^2=0.255$, Adjusted $R^2=0.247$). The results show the valid explained variance of four factors of shopping motivation (“purchase of worthy collectible products”, “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues”, “bargaining enjoyment”, and “purchase of novel and unique products”) on purchasing handicrafts.

f) Purchasing CD

According to a multiple regression analysis, the shopping motivation has a significant explanatory power on purchasing CD ($F=31.541$; $P=0.000$). The adjusted explained variance is 24.1% ($R^2=0.249$, Adjusted $R^2=0.241$). The results show the valid explained variance of four factors of shopping motivation (i.e. “purchase of worthy collectible products”, “bargaining enjoyment”, “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues”, and “memories of Taiwan travel”) on purchasing CD.

2) *Hypothesis H₂: Shopping behavior of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on overall satisfaction of night market*

In this part, overall satisfaction toward night market is viewed as a dependent variable and six items of purchasing snacks, female accessories, electronic products, clothing, handicrafts, and CD are regarded as independent variables to conduct the multiple regression analysis. The results are described in details as follows:

In the multiple stepwise regression analysis of overall satisfaction toward night markets, shopping behavior shows a significant explanatory power on overall satisfaction toward night markets (F=24.057, P=0.000). The adjusted explained variance is 19.3% (R²=0.202, Adjusted R²=0.193).

Table I presents the valid explained variance of four dimensions of shopping behavior (i.e. purchasing snacks, purchasing electronic products, purchasing handicrafts, and purchasing clothing) on the overall satisfaction toward night markets. Among them, the item of purchasing snacks has the highest predictive power ($\beta = 0.253$). The regression equation is as follows:

$$\text{Overall satisfaction on night market} = 1.686 + 0.251 * (\text{purchasing snacks}) + 0.160 * (\text{purchasing electronic products}) + 0.124 * (\text{purchasing handicrafts}) + 0.091 * (\text{purchasing clothing})$$

TABLE I
REGRESSION ANALYSIS OF SHOPPING BEHAVIOR ON OVERALL SATISFACTION TOWARD NIGHT MARKETS

Shopping Behavior	Non-standardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	t value	Significance
	B estimated	Standard error	Beta distribution		
Constant	1.686	0.238		7.075	0.000**
Purchasing snacks	0.251	0.047	0.253	5.344	0.000**
Purchasing electronic products	0.160	0.043	0.188	3.736	0.000**
Purchasing handicrafts	0.124	0.045	0.138	2.746	0.006**
Purchasing clothing	0.091	0.040	0.108	2.287	0.023*

* P ≤ 0.05, **P ≤ 0.01

3) *Hypothesis H₃: Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on post-purchasing behavior*

a) *H_{3.1}: Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on satisfied post-purchasing behavior.*

From the analysis of Pearson correlation matrix as shown in Table II, this study finds there is a significant medium-positive correlation among all variables in between overall satisfaction toward night markets and satisfied post-purchasing behavior. This result presents that the overall satisfaction of Mainland tourist toward night markets has a significant impact on satisfied post-purchasing behavior. The highest correlation of overall satisfaction achieved belongs to the item "I am willing

to revisit Taipei night markets in the future" (0.549). Hence, it is concluded that the highest overall satisfaction of Mainland tourist toward night markets leads to the strongest willingness of revisiting Taipei night markets.

TABLE II
PEARSON CORRELATION MATRIX OF SATISFIED TOURIST IN BETWEEN OVERALL SATISFACTION AND POST-PURCHASING BEHAVIOR

	Overall satisfaction on night market	
	Correlation coefficient	Significance
I am willing to revisit Taipei night markets in the future	0.549	0.000**
I will recommend and disseminate Taipei night markets to friends	0.527	0.000**
I will choose Taipei night markets if I have a chance to vote main sightseeing points of Taiwan	0.517	0.000**
I will disseminate Taipei night markets toward mass media	0.470	0.000**
I will pay attention to new active information on Taipei night markets	0.456	0.000**

* P ≤ 0.05, **P ≤ 0.01

The results of the simple regression analysis respectively show that the explanation power of overall satisfaction toward night markets on the item "I am willing to revisit Taipei night markets in the future" (F=152.310, P=0.000), "I will recommend and disseminate Taipei night markets to friends" (F=135.670, P=0.000), "I will choose Taipei night markets if we have the chance to vote main sightseeing points of Taiwan" (F=128.560, P=0.000), "I will disseminate Taipei night markets toward mass media" (F =99.895, P=0.000), and "I will pay attention to new active information on Taipei night markets" (F=92.769, P=0.000) all reach significance. Therefore, it is assumed that overall satisfaction toward night markets will affect satisfied post-purchasing behavior.

b) *H_{3.2}: Overall satisfaction of mainland tourists has a significant impact on unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior*

Table III shows the results of Pearson correlation matrix analysis. It is noted that there is a significant medium-positive correlation among all variables in between overall satisfaction toward night markets and unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior (i.e. "I will express the bad experience to tour agent or tour guide" and "if I have a bad feeling or problems, I will directly react to shop assistant"). Among them, the item "I will express the bad experience to tour agent or tour guide" expresses the highest correlation with overall satisfaction (0.435). However, it is acknowledged that Mainland tourists still present high overall satisfaction toward Taipei night markets despite their unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior reflected through their reporting of bad experience to the tour agent or the tour guide. Generally speaking, Mainland tourists' overall satisfaction toward night markets would not be affected by unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior.

TABLE III

PEARSON CORRELATION MATRIX OF UNSATISFIED TOURIST IN BETWEEN
 OVERALL SATISFACTION AND POST-PURCHASING BEHAVIOR

	Overall satisfaction on night market	
	Correlation coefficient	Significance
I will express the bad experience to tour agent or tour guide	0.435	0.015*
If I have a bad feeling or problems, I will directly react to shop assistant	0.405	0.024*
I will complain to related units about the bad experience and ask for resolution or amends	0.170	0.361
I would not visit Taipei night market	0.156	0.402
I would suggest relatives not visit Taipei night market	0.143	0.441
I will express the bad experience via the mass media of network, a newspaper office, or radio station	-0.129	0.490

* $P \leq 0.05$, ** $P \leq 0.01$

The simple regression analysis results show that the explanation power of overall satisfaction toward night markets on the items “I will express the bad experience to tour agent or tour guide” ($F=6.757$, $P=0.015$) and “If I have a bad feeling or problems, I will directly react to shop assistant” ($F=5.674$, $P=0.024$) all reach significance. Therefore, it is concluded that overall satisfaction toward night markets will affect unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A. *Mainland tourists' shopping motivation has a significant impact on shopping behavior*

1) *Shopping motivation serves as “personal use” motives toward shopping behavior*

The shopping motivation in terms of “personal use” exerts a significant impact on tourists' purchase of snacks since snacks in the night markets play the role as the most representatives of Taiwanese food culture. Therefore, when travelling to Taiwan, Mainland tourists prefer going shopping at the Taipei Night Markets to enjoy typical snacks.

2) *Shopping motivation serves as “memories of Taiwan travel” motives toward shopping behavior*

According to [5], [11], and [12], the shopping motivation in terms of “memories of Taiwan travel” has a significant effect on tourists' purchase of snacks and CD since these types of souvenirs possess a valuable and symbolic meaning that serve as a validation for the travel experience as well as an effective means to evoke memories that are different from daily-life memories. Therefore, it can be clearly explained why Mainland tourists prefer buying souvenirs at the night markets in order to keep as remembrances and shopping memories.

3) *Shopping motivation serves as “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues” motives toward shopping behavior*

The shopping motivation in terms of “purchase of gifts for family, friends, or colleagues” has a significant influence on

tourists' purchase of snacks, female accessories, electronic products, clothing, handicrafts, and CD. This motivation is especially considered critical toward Mainland tourists since buying gifts to family and friends plays a crucial role in enhancing mutual friendships.

4) *Shopping motivation serves as “bargaining enjoyment” motives toward shopping behavior*

The “bargaining enjoyment” aspect of shopping motivation has a significant impact on tourists' purchase of female accessories, electronic products, CD, and handicrafts. This phenomenon is reflected through the purchase process of Mainland tourists when shopping in night markets, in which they will compare items and then conduct bargaining. Through the bargaining process, Mainland tourist would obtain a reasonable price. Concurrently, discussions with family members or friends during the bargaining process can positively bring shopping activities a pleasant atmosphere.

5) *Shopping motivation serves as “purchase of worthy collectible products” motives toward shopping behavior*

Shopping motivation in terms of “purchase of worthy collectible products” has a significant impact on tourists' purchase of clothing, CD, electronic products, and handicrafts. Therefore, Mainland tourists when shopping in night markets prefer purchasing locally featured souvenirs which are worth collecting such as clothing, handicrafts, CD, etc...

6) *Shopping motivation serves as “demonstration of personal wealth and status” motives toward shopping behavior*

Shopping motivation in terms of “demonstration of personal wealth and status” especially has a significant effect on tourists' purchase of clothing. Mainland tourists favor buying clothing and apparel souvenirs which can be able to not only satisfy their demands but also effectively express their personal wealth and status.

7) *Shopping motivation serves as “purchase of novel and unique products” motives toward shopping behavior*

Shopping motivation in terms of “purchase of novel and unique products” has a significant impact on tourists' purchase of handicrafts. In night markets, Mainland tourists not only go shopping but also can be able to understand Taiwan's current fashion trends and the differences in between Mainland and Taiwan as well as to get new product information.

B. *Mainland tourists' shopping behavior has a significant impact on overall satisfaction toward night markets*

Concerning shopping behavior, the purchase of snacks, electronic products, handicrafts, and clothing exerts a significant impact on consumers' overall satisfaction toward night markets. Therefore, it is concluded that the purchase of delicacies have significant effect on customers' overall satisfaction. Hence, this finding implies that in order to maintain and enhance customer satisfaction, Taipei Night Market vendors and food-stall owners should pay more attention to improve hygiene; art shop owners should enhance

art features and commodity diversification; and the owners of electronic product shops are also recommended to ensure product and service quality.

C. Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on satisfied post-purchasing behavior

1) Overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists has a significant impact on post-purchasing behavior

The data analysis shows that Mainland tourists' overall satisfaction toward night markets and satisfied post-purchasing behavior have a significantly medium-positive correlation. The highest correlation of overall satisfaction and post-purchasing behavior (i.e. "I am willing to revisit Taipei Night Markets in the future") is 0.549. In other words, the highest overall satisfaction of Mainland tourists toward night markets results in the strongest willingness of revisiting Taipei Night Markets. The simple regression results show that all variables of satisfied post-purchasing behavior are significantly affected by overall satisfaction toward night markets.

2) Overall satisfaction of mainland tourists has a significant impact on unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior

Concurrently, it is noted that the data analysis shows a significant medium-positive correlation between Mainland tourists' overall satisfaction toward night markets and unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior. Mainland tourists express unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior by reporting their bad experience to the tour agents or the tour guide.

The simple regression results show that overall satisfaction will be somewhat influenced by unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior, i.e. "I will express the bad experience to tour agent or tour guide", "If I have a bad feeling or problems, I will directly react to shop assistant". However, this study finds that tourists' overall satisfaction toward night markets is still high despite unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior, thus it is concluded that overall satisfaction would not be affected by unsatisfied post-purchasing behavior.

D. Recommendations

Due to the limitation in research scope which is mainly based on Taipei Tourist Night Markets, future studies are recommended to expand the scope of night markets to different regions of Taiwan and further compare the similarities and differences in night market shopping among various regions. Future studies are also suggested to explore and compare various shopping preferences of tourists with different nationalities in order to provide night market stalls' owners with better guidelines for developing practical marketing strategies. Finally, since this study finds out one of the important motivations of Mainland tourists in night market shopping is to memorize the Taiwan visit, it is strongly recommended that night market retailers should develop Taiwan's typical and representative souvenirs (i.e. products with printed pictures of Alishan Mountain, Taipei 101, etc.) in order for tourists to keep as valuable memories.

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